

Mundhumism: Religion, Dharma, and Organic Way of Life

Research-Communication

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Publication Information

Publication: Research Publication Series

Biratnagar, Nepal

2026

Keywords: Mundhumism, Kirat, Yuma-Theba, Sumnima-Paruhang, Organic
Philosophy, Indigenous Knowledge, Nepal

This article will be included in the upcoming book after necessary editing and revisions.

Citation:

Subba, N.R. (2026). *Mundhumism: Religion, Dharma, and Organic Way of Life*. Research
Publication Series. Biratnagar, Nepal. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18771248>

Brief Introduction

The present article provides a comparative analysis of the Kirat community's original thought and way of life, 'Mundhumism', with the concepts of 'religion' and 'dharma' that are prevalent worldwide. Although Kirat Mundhumism is often viewed as an institutional religion or philosophical religion, its basic character is different and unique from both of these.

The main objective of the study is to substantiate on philosophical and practical grounds why Mundhumism is an 'organic' or natural way of life. In the course of the analysis, primitive ancestral concepts such as Yuma-Theba, prevalent in the Limbu community, and Sumnima-Paruhang of the Rai community are kept at the centre. Whereas Western 'religion' emphasises a certain divine text and institutional structure, and Eastern 'religion' explains cosmic laws and the cycle of karma, Mundhumism directly unites human existence with its 'ancestry' and 'nature'.

This article presents three main arguments for considering Mundhumism as 'organic':

1. The relationship between soil and plants: Ingredients such as ginger, fenugreek, and bitter melon used in Kirat rituals show a deep connection to the biological cycles of nature.

2. The Hearth Philosophy: Considering the three-stone hearth of the home as the centre makes it clear that this philosophy is based on the basic needs of human life and family continuity.

3. Ancestor-Nature Axis: In this philosophy, God is not some distant supernatural force but one's own primitive ancestors and the surrounding environment (forests, rivers, mountains).

In conclusion, Mundhumism is not an imported or manufactured idea but a vibrant 'organic' path that has spontaneously evolved along with the historical development of Kirati civilisation. It provides the modern world with an original vision of living in balance with nature and taking pride in its historical identity.

Background

Although terms like ‘Kirat Dharma’ or ‘Yuma Dharma’ have been given priority in government documents, the essence of Mundhum, Yuma-Theba and Sumnima-Paruhang remains alive as the basic foundation in the deep traditions and daily life of the Kirat community. In fact, Mundhum not only encompasses these concepts of primitive ancestors, but also broader life philosophy, values and original practices that cannot be encompassed by religion and dharma. Therefore, it seems more relevant and justifiable to define this overall system as ‘Mundhumism’.

This discrepancy between administrative records and original practice naturally raises a question in the conscious community: are Mundhumvad, religion and dharma really the same, or are they merely equivalent? To clarify this ideological dilemma and establish the true identity of Mundhumvad, a comparative analysis between these three dimensions is presented here.

Religion, Dharma and Mundhumism: A Comparative Analysis

To understand the true depth of Mundhumvad or Kirat-yuma philosophy, it is necessary to compare it with modern ‘religion’ and the popular ‘dharma’. Although these concepts are generally viewed from the same perspective, there are big fundamental differences in their philosophical foundations and practical application:

a) Differences in religion:

Religion in the Western sense is an ‘organised’ and ‘institutionalised’ structure. It has an authoritative book and an ultimate truth. But there is no single ‘ultimate’ book in the Mundhum; it lives on orally in different forms from community to community. The Kirats follow the Mundhum not for an invisible heaven, but rather to follow the path of their ancestors.

b) Difference with Dharma:

In Hindu or Buddhist philosophy, ‘dharma’ refers to the overarching cosmic law. Kirat Mundhum also emphasises ‘duty’, but at its core is ‘soil’ and ‘ancestry’. The Yuma Samyo of the Limbus or the Mundhum of the Rais is not for any philosophical debate but rather

deals with the practices of daily life, farming and the path of the ancestors (Sam-Yama) after death (Subba, 1999).

Why is Mundhumism an ‘organic’ philosophy?

‘Organic’ means ‘growing spontaneously from the soil’, not from a laboratory or artificial idea. Calling Mundhumism ‘organic’ means that it is not a ‘manufactured’ idea from a laboratory or intellectual discussion. It is a way of life that has grown and developed along with the evolution of nature. Some of the main reasons and examples of Mundhumism being organic are:

1. Unity with the biological cycles of nature:

In Mundhum, humans and nature are not separate. For example, the Sakela (Ubhauri-Udhauri) celebrated by the Rai community and the Chasok Tangnam performed by the Limbu community are completely connected to food and seasons. When nature turns a new leaf, the Mundhum consciousness also celebrates the new year. This is an ‘organic’ relationship, where humans are not the masters of nature but rather a small part (Gaenzle, 2002).

Use of natural resources: The materials used in Kirat rituals are completely natural and local. For example, instead of gold and silver, ginger, millet stalks, bitter gourd, and banana leaves are used in worship. These materials are obtained directly from nature by humans.

2. Relationship with soil and vegetation:

The materials used in worship at Mundhum are also organic. Instead of gold, silver or precious metals, Kirats use local and natural items such as ginger, rice, millet stalks (wachipa/tongba), and titepati. The materials used in the construction of the Yuma Sammam Than in the Limbu community show their deep connection to the soil.

3. Ancestral memory and Chulho Darshan:

In Kirat philosophy, God is not in a temple but in the ‘chulho’ (three stones) of the home. In both Rai and Limbu communities, the

three stones of the chulho are considered symbols of ancestors and creation. This is evidence of being 'organic' because it is spiritually connected to the most basic needs of man (food and fire). It is not an artificial structure of a grand temple but rather an organic symbol of the continuity of family and lineage (Rai, 2013).

4. Oral and Living Tradition:

Mundhum is not a written script that has died; it has been alive in the tongues of the Fewa (Phedanba), Samba or Nakchong since the time of the 'Sawa Yehang'. It changes its form according to time and circumstances, but its spirit is always rooted in ancestors and nature. Religion or religious books may be static over time, but Mundhum is alive in the tongues of the 'Phedanba', 'Samba' or 'Nakchong'. It is a 'living' system that has been refined through the experience of generations and interaction with nature (Gaenzle, 2002).

Biological understanding of creation: By interpreting creation through the union of Sumnima-Paruhang or Yuma-Theba, this philosophy seems to link the earth as 'mother' and the sky as 'father' in a biological relationship.

The subtle difference between religion, dharma and secularism

We usually consider 'religion' and 'dharma' to be synonymous, but at the academic and philosophical levels, they have very different meanings, in which the place of Mundhumism is more specific:

Religion: This is an institutional and organised structure. It has a specific founder (Prophet), a single authoritative scripture (Scripture), and strict rules. It often emphasises the 'afterlife' or 'salvation'.

Dharma: This comes from Eastern (Hindu, Buddhist, and Jain) thought in particular. It means 'to hold,' i.e., cosmic laws, morality and duty. It emphasises freedom from the cycle of 'karma' and 're-birth.'

Mundhumism: It is neither an institutional religion nor a mere philosophical religion. It is an ‘organic’ system. It does not have an ‘invisible God’ or a longing for ‘salvation’ at its centre; rather, it has ‘ancestors’ and ‘nature’ at its centre. Yuma-Theba in Limbu and Sumnima-Paruhang in Rai are symbols of ancestors, which connect our blood and soil (Subba, 1999).

Speciality	Religion (Western Religion)	Indic Dharma	Mundhumism
Center point	One God and one scripture.	Cosmic law and duty.	Primitive ancestors and nature.
spread	Proselytisation.	The theory of karma and reincarnation.	Genealogy and Mundhumi rituals.
Temple/Place	A church, a mosque or a grand temple.	Ashram, monastery or collective place.	The hearth, the place, and nature.
Main power	God / Allah / Christ	Gods and Goddesses/Avatars	Sumnima-Paruhang / Yuma-Theba

CONCLUSION

Kirat Mundhumvad is a vibrant and ‘organic’ way of life that has spontaneously emerged from the heart and soil of Kirati civilisation, far beyond the narrow definition of ‘religion’ and ‘dharma’ confined within the narrow circle of any imported theory or written text. This philosophy, reflected in the form of ‘Yuma-Theba’ in the Limbu community and ‘Sumnima-Paruhang’ in the Rai community, teaches us to live with pride in the sacred hearth of our own home, the memory of our ancestors and the warm embrace of nature, instead of dreaming of some imaginary afterlife or invisible heaven. Thus, on the one hand, Mundhum connects people to the deep roots of their blood, lineage and history, while on the other hand, accepting nature as the primordial guardian paves a fundamental and eternal path to living a balanced and dignified life.

Whether it is called ‘Sumnima-Paruhang’ in the Rai community or ‘Yuma-Theba’ in the Limbu community, these original words basically reveal the same philosophical truth of the eternal balance between female and male power and the profound reverence for ancestors. Kirat Mundhumvad is such an original and ‘organic’ path that always keeps people connected to their historical roots. It neither believes in the artificial business of conversion nor does it carry the imposed burden of any foreign culture. In fact, it is a unique and vibrant existence, blossoming from the blood, sweat and fragrance of the Kirats’ own soil.

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